

APPLICATIONS OF ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR AEROSPACE AND AUTOMOBILE

J. K. Yu, H. L. Li, R. Hu and B. L. Shang
National Laboratory of Solidification Processing
Northwestern Polytechnical University
Xi'an, Shaanxi 710072, China

ABSTRACT

Research and development of C/Al and SiCp/Al composites for aerospace and automotive applications are described in this paper. Chemical vapor deposition for functionally gradient coating on carbon fiber, pressure-regulated infiltration for C/Al composites and spray co-deposition for SiCp/Al composites are discussed, with particular emphasis on decreasing the fabrication cost. These advanced fabrication techniques were developed successfully, and C/Al composites with the size up to $\Phi 100 \times 300$ mm and SiCp/Al composites with the weight of 100~150kg have been achieved. A component fabricated by C/Al composites is also illustrated.

Key words: metal matrix composites, design, processing, interface, applications

1. INTRODUCTION

During the last two decades the research and development of metal matrix composites did draw much attention and became gradually more attractive around the world. The application of these advanced materials, however, is still in the early stage. The high cost of advanced composite materials, including the cost of reinforcement materials and fabrication, is a primary barrier to large scale use of composite structures [1]. Among the various composite systems, carbon fiber reinforced aluminum (C/Al) composites and silicon carbide particulate reinforced aluminum (SiCp/Al) composites have potentially great application from the economically point of view. Therefore, It is very important to decrease the fabrication cost of aluminum matrix composites for large quantity use.

Many techniques have been proposed for the preparation of aluminum matrix composites. Of these techniques, liquid infiltration and spray co-deposition are two excellent processes, offering a combination of technical versatility and attractive process economics [2, 3]. For these processes, the interface between reinforcement and matrix is the key problem. In the case of C/Al composites fabricated by liquid infiltration, fiber coating is a potential way to control the interface. Unfortunately, the various coatings proposed before [4], whether they are single coatings or double coatings, only have limited functions, mainly to improve wetting and preventing chemical reactions. A new coating, functionally gradient coating was proposed at the author's laboratory. The coating can be easily fabricated by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and can solve nearly all the problems of interfaces during composite fabrication, as well as during service. Many infiltration methods have been described, and the theory and experiment of infiltration have been studied in detail at MIT [5, 6]. However, these methods usually have difficulties to control the rate of infiltration. A new methods, pressure-regulated infiltration which is operated under lower pressure and vacuum, has been developed at the author's laboratory. For SiCp/Al composites, the interface is also the key problem. Heat transfer mechanisms during spray co-deposition were investigated at University of California [7], and we fo-

cus our research on the surface treatment of SiC particulates and the interfacial reactions in order to control the interface.

As an intermediate step, the development of aluminum matrix composites plays an important role for their high performance applications. At the author's lab, the primary developmental efforts in aluminum matrix composites have been concentrated on C/Al and SiCp/Al composites for aerospace and automotive applications. The major emphasis has been focused on lowering the fabrication cost of large-sized components. This includes speeding up the making of composites, increasing the size of components and automating the fabrication of composite parts. Qualities which make C/Al composites particularly attractive for aerospace applications include: high-temperature capability, very high specific stiffness, excellent thermal conductivity etc [8]. Components in aircraft, missiles and satellites are being developed, and a component for missiles has been successfully manufactured with C/Al composites. In addition, pistons fabricated by SiCp/Al composites are also being developed for automotive applications.

The purpose of this paper is to discuss some of the advanced fabrication methods for aluminum matrix composites, with particular emphasis on decreasing the fabrication cost, and to describe some of the efforts to develop advanced C/Al and SiCp/Al composites for aerospace and automotive applications.

2. RESEARCH

2.1. Processing

Functionally gradient coating on carbon fiber was designed according to physical, chemical and mechanical coordination between carbon fiber and matrix. Generally speaking, the coating consists of three layers and the chemical composition changes gradually from layer to layer. Its inside layer near carbon fiber is pyrocarbon and its outside layer is pure silicon. The intermediate layer between pyrocarbon and pure silicon, namely gradient layer, consists of three sublayers: C/SiC sublayer, SiC sublayer and SiC/Si sublayer. Here, the chemical composition of C/SiC sublayer changes gradually from 100% pyrocarbon to silicon carbide and SiC/Si sublayer from silicon carbide to pure silicon. This design makes the functionally gradient coating have many functions, such as wetting agent, diffusion and reaction barrier, releaser of residual thermal stresses, tailor of interfacial shear strength, etc. The suitable thicknesses of layers can be obtained by calculation and experiment. For instance, the permissible thickness of brittle layer is calculated by [9]

$$C_1 \{F(a/(a+C_1))\}^2 = G_c^* / \pi \epsilon_{fu}^2 E_f \quad (1)$$

where a is the radius of the fiber, G_c^* is the strain energy release rate of the fiber, ϵ_{fu} is the fracture strain of the fiber without brittle layer, E_f is the Young's modulus of the fiber and $F(a/(a+C_1))$ is the geometry correction factor related to relative thickness of fiber and brittle layer. In the case of PAN II type fiber, the calculated value of C_1 is $0.25\mu\text{m}$. Regarding the remains thickness of brittle silicon (no more than $0.05\mu\text{m}$), the thickness of gradient layer, $0.2\mu\text{m}$, is thus selected. Furthermore, the optimum thickness of silicon layer, which is directly related to the processing variables of liquid infiltration, can be calculated and is approximately $0.1\mu\text{m}$. The debonding strength of coated fiber can be adjusted by changing the thickness of pyrocarbon, and in general, the thickness in C/Al composites is $0.1 \sim 0.15\mu\text{m}$.

Chemical vapor deposition is one of the successful fabrication methods for functionally gradient coatings. The structure of coatings, which mainly depends on the deposition temperature and gaseous composition, can be controlled by the temperature field and vapor concentration field in the deposition chamber. In order to make the fabrication process easy and to reduce the cost, a cold wall reactor was used under atmospheric pressure, and source materials such as C_4H_{10} were replaced by cheap-

er reactants such as petrol. Liquid SiCl_4 , hydrogen gas and argon gas were also used as source materials, and the liquid reactants were bubbled by carrier gas before they were introduced into the reactor. In deposition chamber, these source vapors react on the surface of heated carbon fibers to form the functionally gradient coating. For above source vapors, the possible chemical reactions are as follows [10]:

The effect of deposition parameters, such as deposition temperature and gas flow rate, on structure and properties of coatings was investigated according to the kinetics of chemical vapor deposition. The principle of selecting parameters is to obtain high quality coatings at high deposition rate.

A new technique, pressure-regulated infiltration, was developed to fabricate C/Al composites. Infiltration was performed under no more than 1 MPa due to fiber coating. This feature of the process made the fabrication cost much cheaper. The other advantage of this technique is that infiltration rate can be controlled according to infiltration kinetics. In particular, the pressure of fiber chamber and melt chamber can be controlled simultaneously to keep the infiltration process steady. The infiltration rate u is calculated by following equation

$$u = \sqrt{\frac{d_f^2(1-V_f)}{24\mu V_f} \left(P_{mt} + \frac{P_c - P_f}{t} \right)} \quad (5)$$

where μ is the viscosity of the liquid metal, V_f is the volume fraction of coated fiber, d_f is the diameter of coated fiber, P_{mt} is the pressure-regulating velocity of melt chamber, P_c is the capillary pressure which can be calculated for given composite systems, P_f is the pressure of fiber chamber, and t is infiltration time. Besides, fiber temperature and melt temperature can be controlled and measured simultaneously.

Spray co-deposition is a recently developed manufacturing process for SiCp/Al composites which offers a potentially attractive route for decreasing fabrication cost. The process consisted of two basic steps: first, a molten metal stream is atomized using a gas, such as argon; the spray thus produced and particulate are then simultaneously deposited onto a suitably designed plate to produce the composites. The plate is driven downwards at a constant speed and rotates around its axis which is some distance away from the center of atomising nozzle. This design is beneficial to the shape of final products and the temperature field in ingot. To control the interface, several techniques have been developed for surface treatment of SiC particulates, including metallic coating by gaseous reactions, salt coating with aqueous solutions, and heat treatment.

2. 2. Structure

Electron microscopy and microanalysis is one of the key methods to characterize composites so as to optimize the processing of composites and the desired properties and performance. Microstructure of coated fiber, C/Al composites and SiCp/Al composites was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), electron probe microanalysis (EPMA), scanning Auger microscopy (SAM), high resolution electron microscopy (HREM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD).

Figure 1. Morphology of functionally gradient coating on carbon fiber.

Figure 2. Transversal composition profile of the coated fiber by AES.

Figure 3. Micrograph of coated carbon fibers.

Figure 4. Micrograph of coated carbon fiber cloth.

Figure 5. Micrograph of C/Al composite.

Figure 6. Morphology of atomised particles.

The morphology of functionally gradient coating on carbon fiber is shown in Figure 1. In order to see the feature clearly, the thicknesses of three layers were enlarged during fabrication. Figure 2 shows the transversal composition profile of the coated fiber by AES and it confirms that the chemical composition of the coating for C/Al composites is keeping with our creation. The XRD spectra indicate that three layers of the coating consist of amorphous carbon, amorphous or crystal SiC which is related to deposition temperature, and amorphous silicon respectively. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show that each carbon fiber or 2-D fabric (carbon fiber cloth) is uniformly and continuously coated. Using coated fibers, C/Al composites was fabricated by pressure-regulated infiltration. Figure 5 shows that the coated fibers distribute uniformly in aluminum matrix. Both SAM and EPMA confirm that no evident chemical composition changes at the interface except for the mutual solution between silicon layer and aluminum matrix.

The typical morphology of atomised particles is shown in Figure 6. Atomised particles with argon as fine as 22 μm median diameter have been obtained. As shown in Figure 7, the range of particle sizes is approximately from 3 μm to 100 μm . Figure 8 shows the microstructure of SiCp/Al composites fabricated by spray co-deposition. The average size of SiC particulates is approximately 10 μm . The good bond between SiC particulate and aluminum matrix, high density matrix, low-segregation of particulate and volume fraction of SiC particulate up to 15% have been observed through the entire thickness of the SiCp/Al composites. Surface treatment of SiC particulates has good effects on both fabrication process and secondary working process. For example, hot working or joining, which is carried out at temperatures far above the recrystallisation temperature or even above the melting point, makes the SiC particulates cluster if no SiC particulate is coated by wetting agent. Otherwise, the particulates are homogeneously distributed in matrix.

2.3. Properties

The materials evaluated in this study were C/Al and SiCp/Al composites. PAN-based carbon fiber was used and each bundle has 1000 filaments of 6~8 μm in diameter. SiC particulate size used here was 10 μm . The matrices in C/Al and SiCp/Al composites were 356 alloy and 6061 alloy respectively. Evaluation of the C/Al and SiCp/Al composites included tensile properties at room temperature and elevated temperature, fatigue properties, physical properties, tribological properties, etc. Table 1 gives the experimental data and theoretically predicted values of ultimate tensile strength (UTS) for C/Al composites at room temperature. Work carried out has also shown that the tensile strength

Table 1. Longitudinal tensile strength of C/Al composites at room temperature*

Vol% fiber	UTS (MPa)	ROM (MPa)	UTS/ROM
5	301	317	0.950
10	463	474	0.977
15	630	631	0.998
20	780	788	0.990
25	937	945	0.992
30	1093	1102	0.992
35	1250	1259	0.993

Table 2. Tensile properties of SiCp/Al composites at room temperature**

Vol. % SiC	UTS (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Elong (%)
15	450	100	3.0

* * heat treatment; T6

* Number of Specimens tested; 5
 UTS of carbon fiber; 3300MPa
 UTS of 356 alloy; 160MPa

decreased at the elevated temperatures. However, the UTS of C/Al composites at the elevated temperatures up to 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ remained more than 95% of the UTS at room temperature. This excellent tensile strength of C/Al composites can be attributed to the multi-functions of functionally gradient coating during fabrication and service. The typical tensile properties of SiCp/Al composites at room

temperature are shown in Table 2. SiC additions also reduce the wear rate of composites remarkably due to the coating on SiC particulates.

3. DEVELOPMENT

Two types of chemical vapor deposition for functionally gradient coating have been developed; continuous CVD for carbon fiber and semi-continuous CVD for carbon fiber cloth. A schematic illustration of continuous CVD is given in Figure 9. Deposition chamber was divided into three sections and the temperature field and concentration field in each section kept stable during fabrication. The coating rate on carbon fibers has increased 100 times than laboratory scale CVD. A schematic diagram of semi-continuous CVD is shown in Figure 10. There are two important differences between continuous CVD and semi-continuous CVD. One difference is that carbon fibers in continuous CVD move continuously, and that carbon fiber cloth in semi-continuous CVD doesn't move during fabrication. The other difference is that the deposition conditions in continuous CVD keep stable, and that the deposition temperature and gas concentration in semi-continuous CVD change gradually during fabrication. A continuous CVD for carbon fiber cloth is being developed. Besides, functionally gradient coating for 3-D woven fabric is also being developed. In order to reduce the cost and to make the operation easy, a automated process for functionally gradient coating has been under development since 1992.

Figure 7. Size of atomised particles.

Figure 8. Micrograph of SiCp/Al composite.

Figure 9. Schematic illustration of the production equipment for continuous CVD.

Figure 10. Schematic Diagram of the production equipment for semi-continuous CVD.

With the improvement of the equipment and processing of pressure-regulated infiltration, the C/Al composites with the size up to $\Phi 100 \times 300$ mm have been fabricated successfully. In addition to uni-

directional C/Al composites, 2-D and 3-D woven fabrics were also used to fabricate C/Al composites by improved infiltration. Near net shape components in various shapes of C/Al composites have also been obtained, and this makes the pressure-regulated infiltration technique become a real one-step fabrication method.

In order to achieve large-sized components produced by spray co-deposition, most attention has focused on the weight of ingot. Nozzle structure based on design at Imperial College [11], injection method of SiC particulate, especially temperature field in ingot were improved and 100~150kg ingot has been achieved. To improve the properties of SiCp/Al composites, coating on SiC particulates is also under development. Furthermore, the SiCp/Al composites in various shapes have been successfully produced by secondary working techniques, such as extrusion, forging, hot working, etc. Joining of SiC_p/Al composites with other materials or themselves is also being developed for special requirements.

4. APPLICATIONS

The majority of effort in the area of aluminum matrix composites at the author's lab has focused on C/Al and SiCp/Al composites for aerospace and automotive applications. Compressor blades in aircraft engines, components in missiles and pistons in automotive engines have been designed and fabricated. B/Al and SiCp/Al composites for aeronautic and space applications were developed extensively at NASA Lewis, and inexpensive particulate reinforced composites have been successfully developed for automotive engines around the world [12]. Among the components developed by us, one typical application of C/Al composites is a component in missiles. As shown in Figure 11, carbon fiber cloth was used to reinforce aluminum matrix. Specific strength and specific stiffness at elevated temperatures, particularly above 400°C, where polymer matrix composites are limited, are the major concern for the component. Functionally gradient coating on carbon fiber cloth was performed by CVD, and using coated fiber cloth, the component was manufactured by pressure-regulated infiltration. Table 3 provides some properties of this product at 450°C. PAN-based carbon fiber was used and the aluminum matrix was 356 alloy. Four specimens were tested in the as-fabricated condition. The UTS and elastic modulus of carbon fiber averaged 3300 MPa and 230 GPa, respectively. The total volume fraction of carbon fiber cloth was 30%, and the difference of the properties between two directions was no more than 5%.

Table 3. Tensile properties of the product at 450°C.

Density (g/cm ³)	UTS (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)
2.32	712	118

Figure 11. Schematic of a component in missiles.

5. SUMMARY

The world of composites is a world of interfaces. Research effort has been focused on the interface, including the control of processing, characterization of microstructure and evaluation of properties. Functionally gradient coating has been successfully used to control the interface of C/Al composites, thus to control the composite properties. This coating can solve nearly all the problems at the interface during fabrication and service, and the similar coating can be used for other composite systems, such as C/Mg composites.

Primary developmental efforts have been concentrated on decreasing the fabrication cost. Two advanced fabrication techniques, pressure-regulated infiltration and spray co-deposition have been successfully developed to fabricate C/Al and SiC_p/Al composites, and using these cheaper methods, C/

Al composites with the size up to $\Phi 100 \times 300$ mm and SiC_p/Al composites with the weight of 100~150kg have been achieved. These techniques can be used in other composite systems and the aluminum matrix composites fabricated already show very good potential for aerospace and automotive applications.

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AERONAUTIC APPLICATIONS

